

ENGLISH AS A LINGUA FRANCA IN PRACTICE: INSIGHTS FROM EDUCATION, MATERIALS AND LEARNER ATTITUDES

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Abstract: This study reviews how the English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) paradigm influences teacher education, teaching materials, and learner attitudes in English Language Teaching (ELT). Using a narrative review approach, it highlights that while ELF awareness is increasing, practical implementation remains limited.

Keywords: English as a Lingua Franca (ELF); Global Englishes; English Language Teaching (ELT)

Introduction

Due to globalization, English has become the common language for communication among people of various linguistic and cultural backgrounds [1]. In other words, English has become a global medium of communication, functioning as a bridge language between speakers who do not necessarily share the same mother tongue. As [2] emphasizes, English, as an international language spoken by people from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds, can no longer be regarded as the sole property of its native speakers. Indeed, research shows that currently non-native users of English outnumber native speakers by a considerable margin [3]. This demographic and functional shift has fundamentally challenged the traditional “native-speaker ownership” ideology.

In such linguistically and culturally diverse settings, it is unrealistic to focus solely on the linguistic and social norms of English-speaking societies while neglecting the diverse contexts where English serves as a means of communication among people with different linguistic and cultural identities [4]. The evolving sociolinguistic landscape of English calls for a more pluralistic understanding of what constitutes legitimate English use and what linguistic models should guide language teaching. Increasing attention has been directed toward the need to rethink existing ELT practices in light of global shifts in English use [5]. Moreover, challenges to the dominant, monolithic understandings of English have begun to influence perspectives within English language teacher education programs [6; 7].

As a component of the broader framework of Global Englishes, which refers to the many forms and varieties of English used worldwide, English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) has emerged as a particularly influential paradigm [8]. ELF highlights the fact that most English interactions today occur among non-native speakers instead of primarily involving native users [9; 10; 11]. [12] define ELF as “English used as a contact language among speakers of different first languages, whether from choice or through some kind of coercion.” (p. 1). From the ELF perspective, English is viewed as a paradigm in which non-native speakers constitute the majority of users, and linguistic legitimacy extends equally to all English varieties without privileging native-speaker standards [13].

Within the ELF framework, research does not encourage a specific and monolithic variety; rather, it exerts emphasis on the fact that English language speakers need to follow some linguistic characteristics, which are intelligible to English speakers with different linguistic backgrounds [14]. From this perspective, the ultimate goal is not to imitate a native model but to become what [15] describe as “an effective multilingual who is able both to adjust the languages in their repertoire and to translanguage as appropriate in the moment.” (p. 32). This has questioned the traditional English-as-a-Native-Language (ENL) model, which continues to shape practices in English as a Foreign Language and influence Second Language Acquisition research [16].

Although ELF has recently gained wider recognition, many EFL teachers remain uncertain about how to apply its principles in their classrooms, largely due to the limited availability of teaching materials developed from an ELF perspective [17; 18]. Also, recent studies indicate that ELT curriculum and teaching materials continue to reflect Anglophone-centric L1 standards in their evaluation parameter, pedagogical orientations, and the selection of English-speaking settings and accent models presented in classroom activities [19; 20]. This situation inevitably raises concerns about the practical implementation of the lingua franca approach in ELT classrooms across the globe [21]. On this basis, the current narrative review explores how the English as a Lingua Franca paradigm influences three critical dimensions of English Language Teaching: teacher education, teaching materials and learner attitudes. The purpose of this study is to describe how the English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) approach is addressed in the context of teacher education, material development, and learner attitudes in the field of ELT, and to reveal the trends, contradictions, and gaps in the field.

Methodology

This study was conducted using a narrative review approach. The narrative review provides a more flexible framework compared to systematic reviews, allowing the historical and conceptual development, trends, and critical aspects of the topic to be addressed together. Data for this review were collected from the Web of Science (WoS) database. The search focused on academic articles published between 2016 and 2025 within the field of English Language Teaching (ELT) / TESOL.

The inclusion criteria were as follows:

- Publications appearing in peer-reviewed journals,
- Studies that address the theme of ELF within the ELT context,
- Articles written and published in English.

Findings and Discussion

Recent research indicates that teachers generally hold positive attitudes toward the English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) approach, yet they struggle to translate this awareness into classroom practice due to limited pedagogical knowledge and a lack of material support [22; 23]. [10] report that while teachers are aware of the diversity of English varieties, this awareness rarely develops into concrete instructional strategies. Similarly, studies on teachers reveal generally favorable attitudes toward ELF, although the curriculum remains shaped around “native-speaker” norms [24]. Nevertheless, some teachers still associate “correct English” with British or American accents [25]. These findings suggest that while theoretical awareness of ELF has increased in teacher education, the infrastructural and practical foundations for implementation remain underdeveloped. Most programs still offer limited coverage of accent diversity, intelligibility-based assessment, and intercultural awareness, indicating that teacher preparation for teaching diverse forms of English continues to be influenced by a monolithic view of the language.

Studies focusing on textbook and curriculum analysis reveal the dominance of Anglocentric representations in English teaching materials. While British and American cultures were prominently featured in the textbooks [26], visual and thematic elements are generally drawn from “Inner Circle” countries [27]. According to [28], the global diversity of English was only superficially represented, and [29] similarly showed that native-like accents continued to be presented as the standard model. Although educational policies increasingly promote the notion of global English, textbook content often fails to reflect these policy goals [30]. Consequently, teachers face difficulties accessing resources that align with an ELF perspective, reinforcing reliance on standardized, native-speaker norms in the teaching process.

Research examining students’ perceptions of different English accents and varieties shows that their attitudes are largely shaped by notions of prestige, intelligibility, and identity. Studies consistently find that learners tend to regard British and American accents as more “correct” or “prestigious,” while viewing other varieties as “foreign” or “hard to understand” [11; 21; 31]. However, other studies demonstrate that when students are regularly exposed to diverse English accents, they develop more flexible and intelligibility-oriented attitudes [32; 31; 33; 34; 35; 36]. This contrast highlights that learners’ accent preferences and attitudes are largely shaped by their learning environment and the degree of exposure to linguistic diversity.

Conclusion

This narrative review examined the reflections of the English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) approach on three key dimensions within the field of English language teaching: teacher education, teaching materials, and learner attitudes. The findings indicate that while awareness of ELF is steadily increasing, its practical implementation remains limited.

Studies focusing on teacher education reveal that both in-service and pre-service teachers generally hold positive attitudes toward the ELF approach. However, they often lack the pedagogical knowledge, guidance, and material support necessary to translate this awareness into classroom practice. This situation suggests that teacher education programs continue to be shaped by “native-speaker” norms, which restrict the integration of ELF principles into practical teaching contexts. However, research indicates that EFL-aware educational methods are crucial for increasing teachers’ understanding of English as a global language [37]. In this regard, [8] argue that teacher education programs should integrate both theory and practice centered on pragmatic language usage, intelligibility in communication, linguistic adaptability, negotiation, and intercultural understanding. Similarly, [38] emphasizes that language teacher education programs should encourage teachers to redefine English proficiency based on communication efficiency rather than native-like accuracy, foster cultural diversity, and incorporate instructional methods that enable learners to use pragmatic strategies effectively.

Analyses of teaching materials reveal that British and American cultures continue to dominate English language textbooks and curricula. Linguistic and visual elements from “Inner Circle” countries are prominently featured, while the global diversity of English varieties is represented only superficially. However, [21] argues that Modern ELT curricula should demonstrate that English is a changing and flexible language by including awareness of how it is used in locally as well as globally, particularly when students or teachers have little exposure to usage of English and its various varieties in global interactions.

Studies addressing learner attitudes show that students still tend to assign higher prestige to British and American accents. However, when they are regularly exposed to diverse English accents, they are able to develop a more flexible and intelligibility-oriented perspective. Teaching conducted in EFL contexts can challenge traditional attitudes toward English usage, native-speaker norms, accent diversity, and notions of English ownership [37].

In conclusion, the growing recognition that English is no longer tied to a single cultural or geographic center calls for a reassessment of both language education policy and classroom methodologies. Future research should go beyond conventional, native-speaker-centric approaches by adopting a holistic perspective that integrates teacher education, material development, and learner attitudes. Such an approach can help transform the ELF perspective from a purely theoretical concept into a sustainable and practical basis for language teaching across diverse contexts.

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